

ORIGIN, MEANING & DEFINITION OF ORGANIZATION BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract:

Organizational behaviour emerged as a distinct field of study in the late 1950s and early 1960s. on the basis of the belief that all managerial and organizational problem are not technical in nature and an understanding and predictability of human behaviour can help managers make their organizations more effective. The study of human behaviour, being a part of general management can be traced back to 4000 BC, when Egyptian pyramids were built or when the dawn of mankind when people hunted in groups for livelihood and protected their families against hostile environment forces. An organized development of economic science and management as distinct disciplines began around the early 18th century when there was shift from cottage industry to the factory system, which gave birth to the industrial revolution in Europe, specifically in England (UK). The Industrial revolution changed the entire behaviour of the civilized world. *Adam smith* a famous economist was the person who advocated management principles. in the area of division of labour and specialization in 1776. **The present paper** is an honest attempt to attract the attention of the readers towards the **origin, meaning and definition of organization behaviour.**

Kew-Words: Organizational, behaviour, distinct, managerial, problem, industry, factory, revolution, labour.

Introduction:

Over the years many scholars and practitioners have contributed towards an organized study of human behaviour within organizational environment with special consideration goint to Prof. *Elton Mayo* and his Haw thorne experiments. These experiments focused upon an understanding of human needs and desires and their relationship with motivation and performance.

Abraham Maslow in support with *Elton Mayo's* contention and findings presented a theory of individual needs, which is popularly known as need hierarchy. The basic aim of this approach is to increase the organizational effectiveness of its common resources, which could be

achieved properly by taking care of human needs. In general, the lower level needs must be satisfied before the higher level needs arise. A manager should be aware of all these needs and use different methods to motivate workers. This is critical and very significant because the fact that complexity of Man's nature. The management must try to assess what motivates people towards better performance and the necessary steps to create an environment which induces positive and strong motivation.

The behavioral approach had a major impact on management thinker's night through the 1970s and indeed changed the structure of the organization from the bureaucratic to participative in which the workers have more freedom to participate in the affairs of the organization. However, some serious questions have to be answered, as to whether a worker is entirely 'social man' or an 'economic man' This is because of the fact that not all employees seek self-actualization as their ultimate goal. Whereas some professionals may be motivated by recognition and feeling of self-fulfillment, it may be different in case of blue collar workers for whom increased economic benefits are the only motivators. Considering the above observation and the fact that human behaviour is complex, there is a need to study as to know how does an employee behaves in a group or as an individual in the work environment and also as to study what is the motivating factor that increases performance of an employee. The present day challenging business environment and cut-throat competition has given more scope for the study of organisational behaviour.

After knowing the origin of organisational behaviour, let us try to define organisational behaviour and understand the meaning.

“Organisational behaviour is the study and application of knowledge about how people act within organizations. It is a tool for human benefit. It applies broadly to the behaviour of people in all types of organizations. Such as business, government, schools and science organization.

Another definition states that **"Organisational behaviour means that study of the behaviour of individuals and groups in organizations and organizations themselves, as they interact to attain desired outcomes"**.

From the definitions we can assess that the study of human behaviour in work environment is the interface between human behaviour and the organisation, and organization itself study of the individual behaviour alone is incomplete because the action of the employee influences and are influenced by the organization where they work. The influence of the environment on the interface between the individual and the organization cannot be overlooked.

Objective : The objective of the present paper is to attract the attention of the readers towards the origin, meaning & definition of organization behaviour.

Contributing disciplines to organizational behaviour:

The study and understanding of human behaviour has posed a strong challenge to both the scientific thinkers as well as behaviours. Many of them have been concentrating to identify the causes of human behaviour. Science has always been involved in the "cause" and "effect" phenomenon and the relationship between them as to how a "cause" induces "effect". Likewise, the behavioural scientists want to find out why people behave the way they do. They want to find a common denominator of human behaviour which can be generalized and classified into standard causes which result into identifiable and functionally dependent patterns of behaviour. Thus, by discovering and analyzing these causes, the behaviour can be predicted, manipulated and controlled.

OB is concerned with people's thoughts, feelings, emotion and actions in a work environment. To understand an individual's behaviour is in itself a challenge and understanding group behaviour in an organisational environment would be a Herculean managerial task.

The organizational behaviour is specifically concerned with work related behaviour, which takes place in an organization. Organisational behaviour is the synthesis of many other fields of study and is built upon contribution from a number of behavioural disciplines. The predominant area of psychology is concerned with the study of individual behaviour. Also, other behavioural disciplines affect the group dynamics and organization system.

The contributing disciplines to organisational behaviour field are shown in fig 1.2 and a brief description of each field is essential to understand better.

Source: Organisational Behaviour by Jit S. Chandan

Psychology

Psychology is a science that seeks to study, understand, measure, explain and possibly change the behaviour of humans. Relative to organizational environment, it assists in understanding motivation at work, individual and interpersonal perceptions, functioning of personality, effects of training, leadership effectiveness, job satisfaction and attitude measurement. Psychology also studies such behaviour patterns as fatigue, boredom and

monotony which impede efficient work performance. This discipline is considered as fundamental for the study of organisational behaviour.

Sociology

Sociology as a science, has a major impact on the field of organisational behaviour. It involves the study of social systems in which individuals exercise their social roles in relation to their fellow human beings, be it within the family or within the organization. Few of the organizational processes considered are group dynamics, organizational structure, bureaucracy, power and conflict.

Social Psychology

As we have observed that psychology deals with individual behaviour, and sociology deals with group behaviour, the social psychology examines interpersonal behaviour. The social psychologists are concerned with intergroup collaboration, group decision making and integration of individual needs with group activities. Another area under investigation by social scientists is the effect of "change" on individuals and how people adjust to "change" both as individuals and in group context.

Industrial Psychology

Industrial psychology helps to understand the individual reactions to industrial environment. It involves selection and placement of individual into particular jobs through psychological tests, study of mental health as affected by physical industrial environment, impact of organizational structure on human performance and the types of job affecting, safety and morale of workers. Organisational behaviour is an extension of Industrial psychology and in the present situation both the terms have become synonymous.

Anthropology

Anthropology primarily studies the cultural impact on individual behaviour. It is our cultural heritage that builds our value system and our sense of right and wrong which in terms affect our norms of acceptable behaviour. The differences in behaviour under the same set of circumstances can be traced to cultural upbringing and the values learned in the cultural environment. Thus behaviour to some degree, can be predicted on the basis of cultural generalities.

Political Science

Political science even though considered as the study of political system, has many ingredients which directly affect human behaviour in organizations since politics dominates every organisation to some degree. Many themes of interest directly related to organizational

behaviours are political manipulation, allocation of power, conflict and conflict resolution, coalition for power and self-interest enhancement.

Economics

Economics aids in the understanding of economic condition at a given time, economic policies of the government allocation of scarce resources to different competing alternatives and all these factors affect organizational climate. Organizational behaviour has learned a great deal from such economic factors as labour market dynamics, cost-benefit analysis, marginal utility analysis, human resource planning, forecasting and decision making.

Engineering

Engineering, especially the industrial engineering branch, has contributed significantly in the areas of time and motion study, work measurement, work flow analysis, job analysis, job design, wage and salary administration, ergonomics, training and development etc. Each of these areas has impact on organisational behaviour.

Medicine

Medicine is the latest discipline to contribute for organisational behaviour. The primary area of interest is work related stress; tension, fatigue and depression. The study of cause and consequences of stress, fatigue and use of individual drugs, physiotherapy, physical exercise, meditation, yoga to reduce stress is fast becoming an area of study within the organizational environment.

Semantics

Semantics is one of the more recent disciplines, helps in the study of communication within the organization. Misinterpreted and mis directed communication or simply lack of proper communication creates many behavioural problems. Communication as such, is the life line of an organization and flow of information at all levels is very essential for the success of an organization. This study tries to sort out differences in individual interpretations of words and symbols.

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